

ABOUT THE SPIRITUAL AND ARTISTIC WORKS OF ABDULLA AVLONI

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Annotation: information is given about advanced philosophical socio-political thoughts in Central Asia at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century.

Key words: philosophical, socio-political thoughts, modernity, culture, enlightenment, worldview, mysticism, tradition, lifestyle, life and creativity.

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The views of Abdulla Avloni in the field of education are closely connected with the mentality, lifestyle, and national values of the Uzbek people. The rich pedagogical heritage of the writer is the development of educational issues, the moral and meaning of Abdulla Avloni in forming it in the hearts of students. his views in the field of education and upbringing are closely connected with the mentality, lifestyle, and national values of the Uzbek people, the rich pedagogical heritage of the writer, the development of educational issues, and the formation of moral and spiritual perfection in the hearts of students, the national school and it is becoming the need of the hour to study what has served as a valuable source.

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Every nation has its own spiritual image. Today, raising spirituality is one of the highest tasks in our society, which is progressing in every way. In further development of our spirituality, the importance and role of historical artistic and scientific works that artistically reflect the history and spiritual image of our nation is incomparable. Uzbek There are many such works in literature. They are important in bringing the young generation to maturity. In this regard, the famous Uzbek writer Abdulla Avloni's four-part "Literature or National Poems" and "The First Teacher", "Turkish Gulistan or Morals", " Textbooks such as "Second Teacher", "School Gulistoni" are also considered to be characteristic. The ideological completeness of the perfect thoughts in these works, the scientific-theoretical basis of the thoughts on the educational system and concepts are proof of our above opinions. Also, the fact that Abdulla Avloni was embodied as a perfect creator of the first textbooks with his creative heritage, the concepts of education and upbringing, ideological and artistic observations were researched in his works, and the relevance of the topic is the most important today in the work of

the enlightened writer and brilliant creator Abdulla Avloni. The proof of the thoughts on the important issue of education and training is visible in the case of stories, poetic scenes, or metaphorical narratives.

On August 3, 2017, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting with the representatives of the creative intellectuals of our country. In this meeting, many problems arising in the field of culture and art were revealed. At this meeting, there was talk about large-scale work to be carried out in order to radically reform the sphere of culture, mass media, literature and art, new ideas, initiatives and proposals for the education of young talents, development of our culture and literature. stated: "There is another very important issue that will never leave the agenda for us, and I think it is necessary to pay special attention to it, and it is related to the education of our young generation, our children. As our great grandfather Abdulla Avloni said, this issue is really a matter of life or death for us, or salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster. In this sense, the views of Abdulla Avloni in the field of education are closely connected with the mentality, lifestyle, and national values of the Uzbek people. and researching the fact that it served as a national school and a valuable resource for raising spiritually mature young people is becoming the demand of the times. The works created by Abdulla Avloni for the school and the illumination of moral concepts in them are not only an artistic expression of the issue of education, but also a unique historical-pedagogical, It is considered an educational and encyclopedic monument. As we closely familiarize ourselves with Avloni's works, we once again admit that the educational, educational, ideological and philosophical pedagogic wisdoms expressed in his works still amaze us today with their vital meaning. It is worth noting that the principles of humanity, hard work, patriotism and morals, which determine the essence of Avloni's works, have lessons that are very instructive even for the present time.

Avloni was born on July 12, 1878 in the Mergancha neighborhood of Tashkent city. The artist is a writer, a public figure and a talented pedagogue who has made great contributions to the art and literature of the Uzbek people, as well as national culture and public education. He was one of the first to turn the Uzbek theater into a professional theater, contributed to the development of the press and education. He is considered one of the prominent representatives of the Jadid movement, who carried out spiritual and educational work in Turkestan. Avloni's work was highly appreciated and he was awarded the title of "Hero of Labor" in 1925, and the title of "Educator of Uzbekistan" in 1930 for his long-term work in improving Uzbek culture and literature, training employees. Also, the writer was awarded the Order of Merit on September 30, 2020 for his incomparable contribution to the creation of the national education system.

Avloni wrote "Literature or National Poems" consisting of four parts and "First Teacher" (1912), "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics" (1913), "Second Teacher" (1915), "School created textbooks such as Gulistoni (1917). In these works and journalistic articles, he calls the culture, science, school and education of the peoples of the world. At the beginning of the 20th century, there were many alphabets written for new schools. Among them, Avloni's work "The First Teacher" has its own place. When writing it, Avloni relies on Saidrasul Azizi's work "Ustozi avval". Avloni's work "The Second Teacher" is a continuation of the book "The First Teacher". We can tentatively call the first book the alphabet, and the second book the chrestomathy. The book opens with a poem praising school: School makes you a man,

In this poem, Avloni praises the school as a way of salvation for a person, a flower of life, a force that mobilizes people towards perfection. Therefore, it is emphasized that the place of education is the school.

Among Avloni's educational works, "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics" is an important moral and educational work. The work reflects on the idea of science and morality, which calls people to goodness and deters them from evil.

Also, he thinks about the role of child education and says: "If a person's ego is corrupted at a young age, he grew up without education and morals, expecting good from such people is like reaching out from the ground and reaching for the stars." In his opinion, the social environment, family conditions and people around children are important for the composition of moral qualities in children. In the history of Uzbek pedagogy, Avloni defined it as the first "Pedagogy", that is, the science of child education. Avloni divides child education into 4 sections:

1. Time of education.
2. Physical education.
3. Thought education.
4. Thinks about moral education and its importance.

In the "time of education" section, it is necessary to give education from a young age

emphasizes that it is necessary to involve everyone: parents, teachers, government and others. After all, education is not a private matter, but a national social matter. "As a result, education is a matter of life or death for us, salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster," he says.

The author states that the progress of every nation and the state's power depends on the education of generations. 3 Abdulla Avloni..Turkish culture or ethics - Tashkent: Youth Publishing House, 2019. - 96 6. p. 6

4 Abdulla Avloni..Turkish culture or morality - Tashkent: Youth Publishing House, 2019. - 96 6. 11 p.

Education begins from the birth of offspring and continues until the end of life. It consists of several stages - home, kindergarten, school and community education.

Avloni understands the scope of education in a broad sense. It does not limit it to only morality. He emphasizes the importance of taking care of the child's health first.

The work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" promotes the ideas of enlightenment. Adib says about knowledge in the book: "Knowledge is the glory of the world and the honor of the hereafter. Knowledge is a very high and holy virtue for a person. Because knowledge shows us our condition and actions like a mirror."

CONCLUSION:

In short, Avloni's creative heritage is a propagator of the idea of spiritual and educational education. The educational ideas presented in his works serve as a valuable resource for the development of our national spirituality. It is not wrong to say that the work and practical work of this great writer is a lesson for our youth today.

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